

Some Studies on Oscillatory Chemical Reactions involving Coordinated and Uncoordinated Citrate, Acid Bromate in Presence of Mn(II)

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Oscillatory appearance of Mn(III) in an aqueous solution of Mn(II), bromate and citric acid or Iron(III) citrate in aqueous sulphuric acid is a typical redox phenomenon. The reactions between citric acid and acid bromate and also between Iron(III) citrate and acid bromate in presence of Mn(II) have been studied. Studies include time period of oscillation as a function of concentration of the reactants of the system. Mechanism leading to oscillation has been discussed. The experiments are based mostly on the potentiometric techniques. A number of redox experiments have been done to establish the mechanism.

OSCILLATION in homogeneous chemical reaction system is now well established and is being studied theoretically¹⁻⁴ and experimentally⁵. There are several oscillatory chemical reactions which have been investigated in biochemical systems⁶ and have made these reactions a subject of considerable interest. The most extensively studied homogeneous oscillating reaction^{7,8}, is the metal ion catalysed reaction between malonic acid and bromate in sulphuric acid medium. A detailed mechanism for the cerium catalysed reaction between malonic acid and acid bromate has been almost developed^{9,10}. It has been shown that malonic acid in Belousov's reaction can be replaced by several other organic compounds either possessing a reactive methylene group or easily forming such a group during oxidation^{7,8,11,12} (citric acid, acetoacetic acid, oxal acetic acid, maleic acid, acetone dicarboxylic acid, 2, 4-pentane dione, etc.). Till recently the presence of reactive methylene group was maintained to be necessary for oscillation but the recent report¹³ has shown oscillation in acetylene dicarboxylic acid where there is no reactive methylene group.

The present communication deals with the studies on Mn(II) catalysed reaction between citric acid and potassium bromate in sulphuric acid and also between Iron(III) citrate and acid bromate. Our studies include measurement of time period of oscillation as a function of the concentration of the reactants of the system, i.e., dependence of time period of oscillation on the concentration of (a) potassium bromate, (b) sulphuric acid, (c) Iron(III) citrate and citric acid, (d) manganese sulphate and (e) also its dependence on the temperature. Both the systems have been studied under the same experimental conditions and have been compared. Mechanism and stoichiometry of the overall reaction has been

proposed. A number of experiments on the oxidation of Iron(III) citrate and citric acid with Mn(III), BrO₃ and Br₂ have been done in aqueous sulphuric acid for the purpose.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical grade (B. D. H., E. Merck). Following procedure was adopted to study the oscillatory characteristics of Mn(II) catalysed reaction between acid bromate and Iron(III) citrate and also acid bromate and citric acid.

The reaction cell was kept in an air thermostat with an accuracy of $\pm 0.05^\circ$. The reaction was followed potentiometrically with the measurement of E.M.F. of the system at different time intervals, using a bright Pt electrode coupled with a calomel reference electrode. As Cl⁻ ion inhibits oscillatory phenomenon, ammonium nitrate bridge was used instead of KCl salt bridge. E.M.F. vs time was plotted on graph paper and with its help time period was found out as has been discussed earlier^{14,15}. Time period for the system containing Iron(III) citrate has been represented by Tc whereas for the system containing citric acid as T.

Redox experiments were done by a modified method of Gyani and Prasad¹⁶. Redox experiments with Mn(III) have been done in 9N H₂SO₄ at room temperature (25°). Other redox experiments have been done in 3N H₂SO₄. M/20 Manganic sulphate was prepared by Ubbelohde method¹⁷. This was quite stable for 24 hrs.

Results and Discussion

Oscillations were recorded five times under the same experimental conditions and high degree of reproducibility was observed. Pt electrode showed oscillations in the concentration of oxidised and reduced form of the metal ion which has been used as catalyst which also caused oscillation in the solution colour. Time periods in both the systems were found dependent on several parameters namely concentration of the reagents, acidity and temperature.

(a) Dependence of time period of oscillation on the concentration of bromate

Experiments were carried out for both the systems in $3N H_2SO_4$. Time period of oscillation was found out at different bromate concentrations, keeping the concentration of other components of the system constant. Time period of oscillation decreased with the increase of bromate concentration in both the systems. Time period of oscillation for the system containing Iron(III) citrate was slightly more frequent than that of the system containing citric acid. It has been discussed earlier^{1,2} how does bromate ion act on oscillatory characteristics and also its mechanistic aspect. Results have been listed in Table 1. The system in which Iron(III) citrate

TABLE-1

[IC]=[0.04M], [CA]=[0.04M], [MnSO₄]=[0.01M] in 3 N H₂SO₄,
Temp. 29°±0.05°

No. of Exp.	[BrO ₃ ⁻]	Tc in sec	Tin sec
1	0.05 M	70	75
2	0.04 M	75	90
3	0.03 M	95	110

was taken took more time to initiate oscillation in comparison to the system containing citric acid but when it initiated became more frequent.

(b) Dependence of time period of oscillation on the acid concentration

Experiments were carried out at different acid concentration keeping the concentration of other components constant at constant temperature. Trends were similar as was observed in the case (a). Results have been shown in Table 2. Acidity

TABLE-2

[IC]=[0.04M], [CA]=[0.04M], [BrO₃⁻]=[0.04M],
[MnSO₄]=[0.01M], Temp. 29°±0.05°

No. of Exp.	[H ₂ SO ₄]	Tc in sec	Tin sec
1	1 N	255	270
2	2 N	135	145
3	3 N	75	90

accelerated the reaction of the system so with the increase of acidity, oscillation become frequent.

(c) Dependence of time period of oscillation on the concentration of substrate

Time period of oscillations were found out at various concentrations of Iron(III) citrate and also for various concentrations of citric acid at similar experimental conditions. No significant change could be observed in time period of oscillation with the variation in the concentration of substrate of the system. Table 3 shows the result.

TABLE-3

[BrO₃⁻]=[0.04 M], [MnSO₄]=[0.01 M] in 3 N H₂SO₄,
Temp. 32°±0.05°

No. of Exp.	[IC] and [CA]	Tc in sec	Tin sec
1	0.05 M	68	78
2	0.04 M	65	72
3	0.03 M	60	65

(d) Dependence of time period of oscillation on the concentration of catalyst (Manganous sulphate) in the system

Usually all experiments were carried out when the concentration of manganous sulphate was 0.01M in the system. When this concentration was slightly increased or decreased in a particular experimental set-up, there was practically no change in the time period of oscillation but when it was much raised or lowered, time period of oscillation was observed to be much affected. When concentration of manganous sulphate was 0.1M oscillation disappeared in both the systems only after 2 cycles. On the other hand, when the concentration of manganous sulphate was 0.001 M, it took much time to initiate oscillations in the system. Results have been given in Table 4.

TABLE-4

[IC]=[0.04 M], [CA]=[0.04 M], [BrO₃⁻]=[0.04 M] in 3 N H₂SO₄,
Temp. 32±0.05°

No. of Exp.	[MnSO ₄]	Tc in sec	Tin sec
1	0.001 M	75	68
2	0.01 M	55	76
3	0.1 M	60	90

(e) Effect of temperature on the time period of oscillation

Time period of oscillations have been found out at different temperatures for a particular experimental set-up and have been listed in Table 5. It

TABLE-5

[IC], [CA], [BrO₃⁻]=[0.04 M], [MnSO₄]=[0.01 M] in 3 N H₂SO₄

No. of Exp.	Temp. °C	Tc in sec	Tin sec
1	29°	75	90
2	32°	55	70
3	35°	35	45

was observed that time period of oscillation was much dependent on temperature. Slight change in temperature caused a sharp change in the time period of oscillation.

The system in which Iron(III) citrate was used as substrate source behaved almost the same way as the system containing citric acid. Only slight change in the time period was observed. Iron(III) citrate dissociates in sulphuric acid as follows :

and then behaves like that of the system containing citric acid. Spectral studies^{1,8} of the complex in acid also supports it.

Oscillatory reaction is a typical redox reaction in which metal ion catalyst cycles from reduced form to the oxidised form or *vice versa*. One part of it is supposed to be the oxidation of compound serving as substrate in the reaction by the oxidised form of the metal ion (Mn^{3+}) which is produced as a result of reduction of bromine(V) by Mn^{2+} in the system and another is the reduction of bromine(V) by the reduced form of the metal ion catalyst (Mn^{2+}). In this case Mn^{3+} is produced as a result of reaction of bromate with Mn^{2+} in the system. Mn^{3+} decarboxylates citric acid and the bromo product. The formal reduction potential of the $\text{Mn}^{3+} - \text{Mn}^{2+}$ coupled being 1.4V and acts as one equivalent oxidant.

Redox experiments showed that action of Mn^{2+} over citric acid and Iron(III) citrate was very fast. The result suggested that both citric acid and Iron(III) citrate consumed only 16 equivalents. Solutions of Iron(III) citrate and citric acid were of strength M/360 whereas that of Mn^{2+} was M/20. The reaction could not proceed any further even after prolonged storage of the reaction mixture. Results showed the stoichiometry of the reaction as follows :

The presence of formic acid was confirmed. It was extracted from the reaction mixture with ether in the presence of ammonium sulphate and titrated it by mercurimetric technique^{1,9}. It was found that one mole of formic acid was formed as a result of oxidation of one mole citric acid. Noyes and co-worker also reported that formic acid is inert towards oxidation with one equivalent oxidants^{2,0}.

Bromate failed to react either with citric acid or Iron(III) citrate. Oxidation was also tried with bromine but the rate was quite insignificant in comparison to the reaction of Mn(III) with either citric acid or Iron(III) citrate.

Mn(II) which is produced as a result of decarboxylation of the substrate by Mn(III) in the system, reduces bromine(V) and again Mn(III) is produced.

Thus Mn(III) repeatedly decarboxylates the substrate. Our studies on the reduction of bromine(V) with Mn(II) suggested the formation of BrO_2 , HBrO_2 and HOBr . Formation of hypobromous acid was prominent and was confirmed^{2,1}. The stoichiometry observed was

This is also supported by the observation of Thompson^{2,2}. Degn^{2,3} suggested the reaction as follows :

Free bromine was not found in the system even in trace amount. Our findings suggested oxybromine compound responsible for bromination of the substrate in the system. As we have not isolated bromo derivative from the reaction system, we are not very sure about the bromination mechanism.

When the concentration of bromate is increased in the system, it is always available for converting Mn(II) into Mn(III). Mn(III) is thus repeatedly produced and decarboxylates the substrate in the system, finally the concentration of bromate and the substrate falls in the system and oscillation ceases.

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